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AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION (LIC) OF INDIA

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Abstract

The contribution of insurance sector in any economy has the crucial importance. Life insurance has in olden times been an important method through which individuals with relatively low incomes have been able to save and invest effectively for the longer term. Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India is the main public sector insurance company of India. The present study is an attempt to evaluate the financial performance of Life Insurance Company of India. The main objective behind the study is to measure the performance regarding operational efficiency of the company. The performance of LIC of India has been checked through annual premium received, number of policies and sum assured in India.

Keywords: Insurance, Performance, LIC, Premium, Sum Assured.

Introduction

Service sector of transition economies had experienced a rapid growth over the last decade, indicating the increased importance of this sector to country financial development. The share, in term of GDP, of service sector in Indian economy went up further to 66.8 per cent in 2011-12 (65.5 per cent in 2010-11), because of better performance of this sector in absolute as well as relative (to Agriculture and Industrial sector) sense. Within the service sector, the 'financing, insurance, real estate and business remain the

largest component with 17.9 per cent share in the Indian economy.’ (IRDA Annual Report 2011-12) Insurance, becoming one of the exigent financial services just as Banking, Mutual funds and wealth management, occupies an importunate position in financial sector of economy. Insurance facilitates economic development of country through Risk management, Protection of assets and Mobilisation of saving, leading to capital formation of country. The Historical perspective of insurance sector reveals that nationalisation had given flair of risk to number of problems in area of operational efficiency, image, productivity, and quality of portfolio of system, raised the need for insurance sector reform, aimed at creating more efficient and competitive financial system suitable to requirement of economy.

The year 1999 saw an upheaval in the Indian Insurance Sector, as major sea changes took place with ending of government monopoly, and passage of Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) bill, lifting entry restriction for private players and sanction to foreign player to enter the market with some limit on foreign ownership. At this cross section, the role of the regulator becomes critical, Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) is in finalisation stage vis a vis most of its regulation, which would be instrumental in navigating the future course of insurance industry. IRDA has introduced certain regulations to improve disclosure, profitability and capital as well as consumer protection.

Table – 1 The Milestones of Insurance Regulations in the 20th Century

Year	Event
1912	The Indian Life Insurance Act
1928	Indian Insurance Companies Act
1938	The Insurance Act: Comprehensive Act to regulate insurance business in India
1956	Nationalization of Life Insurance Business
1972	Nationalization of General Insurance Business
1993	Setting up of Malhotra Committee
1994	Recommendations of Malhotra Committee published
1995	Setting up of Mukherjee Committee
1996	Setting up of (interim) Insurance Regulatory Authority (IRA) & Recommendations of the IRA
1997	Mukherjee Committee Report submitted but not made public
1997	The Government gives greater autonomy to Life Insurance Corporation, General Insurance Corporation and its subsidiaries with regard to the restructuring of boards and flexibility in investment norms aimed at channelling funds to the infrastructure sector
1998	The cabinet decides to allow 40 per cent foreign equity in private insurance companies - 26% to foreign companies and 14 per cent to Non-resident Indians and Foreign Institutional Investors
1999	The Standing Committee headed by Murali Deora decides that foreign equity in private insurance should be limited to 26% The IRA bill is renamed the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Bill.
1999	Cabinet clears Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Bill
2000	President gives Assent to the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Bill

Source: Sinha T. (2005). CRIS Discussion Paper Series- 2005 III, The University of Nottingham, Mexico.

Insurance sector has undergone a phenomenal change after liberalisation. Earlier, Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India was the only meant for insurance. But presently, flair of wind change, private sector has been shown tremendous growth in term of better customer service and aggressive marketing strategies and gives tough better competition to LIC. In spite of these, LIC rules the roost with a market share of 70 per cent and become unshakable mainly due to its brand and its sheer reach. LIC has powerful network of coverage, launching attractive advertisement at regular interval to create awareness among general public and introducing phenomenal business strategies by offering colourful scheme products. Simultaneously, the private life insurance companies are also taking much pain to cover up the major population under their boundary, for that purpose they are sponsoring series of effective awareness programme through attractive advertisement.

Apart from exhaustive competitive pressure, the competitive market are in the national interest because they generally business house and individuals' greater choice and better value than alternative approach. (Skipper Jr. & Klein; 2000) Besides all, it is of interest to examine financial performance of LIC, to determine its standing in India's insurance sector and contribution to economic development. Analytical study of financial performance of insurance sector turn out to be very important for analyse financial position. Financial analysis give complete picture on efficiency with which fund entrusted to management has been deployed. In addition to these, this attempt to furnish relevant information for its various users like creditors, bankers, financial institutions, equity shareholder, suppliers, customers and government etc., for their decision making.

The preset study consists of five parts: The first part of the paper gives a brief discussion about the paper title. Section two point outs statement of problem, discussed the literature related to insurance sector and financial performance. Third section discussed the objectives, hypothesis, methodology and scope of study. Data analysis and interpretation are containing in section four. Finally section five offers conclusion and discussion.

Review of Literature

There are a number of studies that have approached to the evaluation the performance of a company. Some pioneer works have been undertaken to evaluate performance of companies but very few studies have been done on financial aspects and its impact on LIC. None of the study reviewed by the researchers examined the financial aspects of any public sector organization especially LIC, on the parameter of sum assured, number of policies and premium received. Hence, the present study attempts to analyses the financial performance of LIC. Some reviews related to financial performance evaluation are as follows;

Tone, K. Sahoo, B.K. (2005) used Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) to examine the performance trends of Life Insurance Corporation of India by employed model for the period of 1982-83 to 2000-01. The result of the study indicated a significant variability in overall and scale efficiency over the 19 years study period. There has been a downward trend in cost efficiency since 1994-95 due to huge initial fixed cost of modernizing their operations, however the year 2000-01 reversing the trends showing a significant increase in cost efficiency due to reaping fruits of modernization. Singh M. and Kumar R. (2009) have found that private sector general insurance companies presents better performance in term of expense management ratio, underwriting result ratio, combine ratio, and public sector insurance companies have strength respect of net earnings and return on net worth ratio.

Kumar R. (2010) in his study revealed that public sector general insurance companies have higher underwriting loss than Private sector general insurance companies, but higher investment income of public sector has compensated their high underwriting loss, leading to higher profitability than private sector general insurance companies.

Rajendran R. and Natarajan B. (2010) analyze the impact of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization (LPG) on LIC using method of least square and trend analysis, and found that total business of Life Insurance Corporation of India are showing an increasing trend.

Bawa S.K. and Kaur N. (2011) determined the technical efficiency, pure technical efficiency and scale efficiency of 10 general companies, comprising 4 public sector general insurance companies and 6 private sector general insurance companies, using Data Envelopment Analysis from the year 2002-2003 to 2009-10. The result of study have concluded that overall efficiency of general insurance companies have been showing an improvement over the period of study. However the sector wise performance analysis states that the technical efficiency of the public sector insurers' i.e. 96 per cent has been better than that of the private sector companies i.e. 89 per cent.

Modi, M.S. (2011) analyzed financial performance of general insurance sector through the tool like Ratio analysis, Fund flow analysis, Cash flow analysis, vertical and horizontal analysis, and come to know that

profitability of the general insurance sector improved over the years. Shinde S.R. (2011) compared cost efficiency and financial performance, of Life Insurance Corporation of India and Private sector insurance companies, in term of New Business and Total Premium. Result of study found that Life insurance corporation of India consistently secured a cost efficiency score of one in all years from 2000-01 to 2009-10, while in case private insurance companies cost efficiency score has been inconsistent.

Gulati N.C. and Jain C.M. (2011) analyzed performance of the players on parameters viz.- agency-force ,premium income, number of policies ,the growth rates of premium, the growth rates of policies, which reflected that the entry of private players in life insurance has resulted in a drop in the market share for Life Insurance Corporation, even than LIC is a growing organization with assets of over Rs 8-lakh Crore.

Chakrabarty J. and Sengupta P.P. (2012) have used Data Envelopment Analysis to compare the performance and efficiency of 13 life insurance companies, in term of Catch-up Efficiency and Frontier Efficiency Scores and Malmquist Total Factor Productivity growth index, for 7 years period ranging from 2003-2004 to 2009-10. They have concluded, LIC reflected a consistent Total factor productivity change index more than 1 indicating relative progress in total factor productivity growth. However all Private life insurers reflected a mean positive total factor productivity growth.

Noronh, M.R. Shinde, S.R. (2012). studied cost efficiency score of life insurance sector in India using the technique of Data Envelopment Analysis during the period from 2000-01 to 2009-10. The result of study found that LIC has consistently secured a cost efficiency score of one in all years from 2000-01 to 2009-10 and secured highest rank for all years under study. However private life insurers companies have been showing an inconsistent cost efficiency score.

Neelaveni V. (2012) randomly selected five life insurance companies at the time of 2002-03 and evaluated their financial performance and found although LIC is big public sector company, in the past a decade period but it lagged behind in some of the financial aspects. However the financial performance of other private life insurance companies was good in some aspects. Rao M.S. Ramana A.V. (2012) analyzed operating performance of National Insurance Company Ltd in terms of the number of products introduced over a period of fire, ages of claims, year-wise settlement of grievances, motor third party cases compromised through various fields, which found that performance is flight specially in area new product performance.

Joo, B.A. (2013) showed the solvency position of Indian non life insurers, in context of Insurance Solvency International Limited (ISI) predictors and the impact of firm size, investment performance and liquidity ratio on their solvency position, by applying Multiple Regression Analysis on a sample of 12 countries from 2004-05 to 2008-09. Result of the study found that claim ratio and firm size have greater impact on solvency position of non life insurance companies.

Venkatesh M. (2013) made a modest attempted to understand growth of insurance sector in India by reviewing premium trend analysis to obtain trend percentage of variables. The result of study found that trend percentage has been continuously increasing indicating favourable growth rate of insurance sector.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the financial performance of Life Insurance Corporation (LIC). The sub objectives of present study are as follows:

- To study the history and growth of Insurance sector.
- To study the history and growth of Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India.
- To evaluate the business performance of Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) of India.

Hypotheses of the Study

Ho₁: There is a insignificant difference in actual and trend values of Premium received in LIC India.

Ho₂: There is a significant difference between actual and trend values in terms of number of Policies received in LIC, India.

Ho₃: There is a insignificant difference in actual and trend values of Sum Assured received in LIC, India.

Methodology of the Study

The study is primarily based on secondary data which have been obtained from the Annual Reports and website of LIC. In order to measure the operational efficiency of LIC, researchers adopted statistical tools i.e. Trend Analysis, ANOVA, F test .

Scope and Period

The scope of the study is limited to Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC), a public sector unit of India. The researcher has selected only LIC for the study. The present study is limited only ten years from 2001-02 to 2010-11. The study covers the performance analysis of three important variable i.e. annual premium received, No. of policies and sum assured received by LIC.

Data Analysis

Performance Measures of LIC

We have taken only three variables for check the performance of Life Insurance Corporation, which are as follows:

- Annual Premium
- Number of Policies
- Sum Assured

Individual Insurance by LIC

Business of individual insurance in India includes the performance of the corporation in terms of total annual premium, number of policies and sum assured during a particular.

In the present paper the trend has been fitted by Least Square method by the researcher through using the Linear Trend Line Method which is also called as the ordinary least-squares (OLS) regression line. The least-squares line uses a straight line

$$y = a + b (x)$$

Trend lines are graphical representations of trends in data that you can use to analyze problems of prediction. Such analysis is also called regression analysis. By using regression analysis, you can extend a trend line in a chart beyond the actual data to predict future values.

Table – 2 Annual Premium Received by LIC Ltd.

Year	Annual Premium (Rs. in Crores)	Trend Values	Trend Indices
2000-01	8852	9855	100.00
2001-02	16009	10779	180.85
2002-03	12505	11703	141.27
2003-04	12541	12627	141.67
2004-05	11224	13551	126.80
2005-06	15158	14475	171.24
2006-07	11673	15399	131.87
2007-08	9872	16323	111.52
2008-09	16859	17247	190.45
2009-10	20949	18171	236.66
2010-11	23586	19095	266.45
Total	159228	159225	
Mean	14475		
CAGR	9.32		

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11

Table 2, exhibit the Annual Premium received by LIC from 2000-01 to 2010-11 in India. With the help of the annual premium trend values have been calculated which is plotted in Chart 1. If we observe only the trend values calculated in Table 2 then we can analyse that there is an increasing trend in the values which means the Annual premium Received in India by LIC is increasing every year. The premium received in 2000-01 by LIC was Rs.8852 crore which fluctuating during the study period and then increased to Rs.16009 in the very next year i.e., in 2001-02. Further the value of Annual Premium was declined in next 3 years and stood at Rs.11224 crore in 2004-05. Thereafter, the Annual Premium was fluctuated trends over in the years and finally reached at a level of Rs. 23586 crore in 2010-11. Trend indices shows that the growth in premium received by LIC by 266.45 times during the study period. The compound annual growth rate of premium received by LIC is 9.32 per cent.

Chart - 1 Annual Premium Received in India

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11

Chart 1 displays the graph of the Annual Premium Received by the LIC in India and its trend for the period from 2000-2001 to 2010-2011. The years are plotted on the X-axis and the Amount (in Crores) is plotted on the Y-axis. The trend has been calculated in Table 1 and has been fitted by least square and is plotted accordingly. A trend line is considered to be more reliable when its R-squared value is at or near 1. The value of R-Square shows how closely your trend line follows the data. The value of R^2 appears on the chart. With a trend line the value of R^2 is 1. As you can see by the chart the trend line follows the data very closely. The straight line (linear) trend line shows the increasing trend of Annual Premium of LIC in India every year. It is best fit line as the value of R^2 is exactly equals to 1 this mean that the line is best fit to the equation and this trend line can be used to forecast the future trend.

Table – 3 F-Test Two-Sample for Variances of Annual Premium Received in India

	Annual Premium	Trend Value of A.P.
Mean	14475.273	14475
Standard Deviation	4607.312624	3064.561306
Variance	21227329.618	9391536
Observations	11	11
Degree of freedom	10	10
F	2.260	
P(F<=f) one-tail	0.107	

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11 by using SPSS

Table – 4 Number of Policies Received in India by LIC Ltd.

Year	No. of Policies	Trend Values	Trend Values
2000-01	19656663	20901309	100.00
2001-02	22491304	21706383	114.42
2002-03	24268416	22511457	123.46
2003-04	26456320	23316531	134.59
2004-05	21817967	24121605	111.00
2005-06	29284800	24926679	148.98
2006-07	20910041	25731753	106.38
2007-08	17961363	26536827	91.38
2008-09	29322395	27341901	149.17
2009-10	30578367	28146975	155.56
2010-11	31445829	28952049	159.98
Total	274193465	274193469	
Mean	24926679		
CAGR	4.36		

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11

The statistical results are given in a table 3. This table contains the mean, variance, count of observations and the degree of freedom for both variables. The output table also includes the F-value, the one-tailed probability for the F-value, and the F Critical value for one-tailed test and the corresponding values for a two tailed test. The mean value of annual premium received in India is Rs. 14475.27 and its standard deviation and variance were 4607.31 and 21227329.6 respectively. The critical value of annual premium is 0.107 which is more than 0.05 and it leads to the acceptance of null hypothesis. It is cleared that there is no significant difference in actual and trend values of Premium received in India.

Table 4 depicts the Number of LIC Policies in India. If we observe only the trend values calculated in above table, that there was 19656663 policies were registered in 2000-01, which increased over the year 2003-04 by 26456320. There after a fluctuation come increasing trend was shown by the analysis. Finally 2010-11 the company registered a significant number of policies i.e., 31445829, from the analysis it is clearly noticed that there is a growth of 160 per cent in number policies received by LIC during the study period.

Chart – 2 No. of Policies Received in India

Chart 2 displays the Number of Policies by the LIC in India and its trend for the period from 2000-2001 to 2010-2011. The years are plotted on the X-axis and the Amount (in Crores) is plotted on the Y-axis. The trend has been calculated in Table 2 and has been fitted by least square and is plotted accordingly. A trend line is considered to be more reliable when its R-squared value is at or near 1. The value of R-Square shows how closely your trend line follows the data. The value of R² appears on the chart. With a trend line the value of R² is 1. As you can see by the chart the trend line follows the data very closely. The straight line (linear) trend line shows the increasing trend of Number of Policies of LIC in India every year. It is best fit line as the value of R² is exactly equals to 1 this mean that the line is best fit to the equation and this trend line can be used to forecast the future trend.

Table – 5 F-Test Two-Sample for Variances of Number of Policies in India

	No. of Policies	Trend Value of Policies
Mean	24926678.64	24926679
Standard Deviation	4728073.198	88441.11666
Observations	11	11
Df	10	10
F	3.135480436	
P(F<=f) one-tail	0.042825456	

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11 by using SPSS

Table 5 presents the statistical analysis of number of policies received by LIC Ltd. On an average the company received 24926678 policies during the study period while, the standard deviation was 4728073. The 'P' value was 0.04 which is less than 0.05, which leads to the rejection of null hypothesis. It can be concluded that there is a significant difference between actual and trend value of number of policies.

Table – 6 Sum Assured Received in India by LIC Ltd.

Year	Sum Assured	Trend Values	Trend Indices
2000-01	124772	115530	100.00
2001-02	192572	142196	154.34
2002-03	179512	168862	143.87
2003-04	198707	195528	159.26
2004-05	179481	222194	143.85
2005-06	283764	248860	227.43
2006-07	201621	275526	161.59
2007-08	173663	302192	139.18
2008-09	363136	328858	291.04
2009-10	396701	355524	317.94
2010-11	443532	382190	355.47
Total	2737461	2737460	
Mean	248860		
CAGR	12.22		

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11

Table 6 shows the actual trend values of Sum assured received by LIC in India, with the help of the Sum Assured trend values have been calculated which is plotted in Chart 3. Sum assured was 124772 in 2000-01, which steeply risen and stood to 283764 in 2005-06. The company has registered a significant growth in Sum Assured during the study period. We can analyse that there is an increasing trend in the values which means that the Sum Assured Received in India is increasing every year. Finally it reached at its highest level of 443532 in 2010-11. From the analysis it is cleared the company has registered a growth of 355 per cent throughout the study period.

Chart 3 displays the graph of the Sum Assured Received by the LIC in India and its trend for the period from 2000-01 to 2010-11. The years are plotted on the X-axis and the Amount (in crore) is plotted on the Y-axis. The trend has been calculated in Table 6 and has been fitted by least square and is plotted accordingly. A trend line is considered to be more reliable when its R-squared value is at or near 1. The value of R-Square shows how closely your trend line follows the data. The value of R^2 appears on the chart. With a trend line the value of R^2 is 1. As you can see by the chart the trend line follows the data very closely. The straight line (linear) trend line shows the increasing trend of the Sum Assured Received in India every year. It is best fit line as the value of R^2 is exactly equals to 1 this mean that the line is best fit to the equation and this trend line can be used to forecast the future trend.

Chart – 3: Sum Assured Received in India

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11

Table – 7 F-Test Two-Sample for Variances of Sum Assured

	Sum Assured	Trend Value of Sum Assured
Mean	248860.0909	248860
Standard Deviation	106123.3429	88441.11666
Variance	11262163903	7821831116
Observations	11	11
Degree of Freedom	10	10
F	1.439837263	
P(F<=f) one-tail	0.287514415	

Source: Annual Reports of LIC & IRDA from 2001-02 to 2010-11 by using SPSS

The statistical results are given in a table 7. This table contains the mean, variance, count of observations and the degree of freedom for both variables. The output table also includes the F-value, the one-tailed probability for the F-value, and the F Critical value for one-tailed test and the corresponding values for a two tailed test. The mean value of Sum Assured received in India is Rs. 248860 crore and its standard deviation and variance were 106123.34 and 11262163903 respectively. The critical value of Sum Assured is 0.287 which is more than 0.05 and it leads to the acceptance of null hypothesis. It is cleared that there is no significant difference in actual and trend values of Premium received in India.

Discussions

LIC is the leading public sector insurance company in India. The company is focusing in expand its business operations in India and outside India. From the analysis and interpretation of available data it has been cleared that the Life Insurance Company enhanced its business operation by policies, annual premium and sum assured. The main findings of the study are as follows---

- The performance in terms of Annual Premium received by LIC was not quite satisfactory in the first half of the study period, where as it perform better in the rest of the study period.

- From the analysis it is found the company is generating revenue through its business operations.
- Analysis of number of policies indicates that the company reached large number of customers as it has registered a significant growth in the study period.
- The company registered a significant growth in sum assured received in India during the study period.

Concluding Remarks

From the above discussion on LIC we may conclude that the performance of Life Insurance Corporation during the period under study is fluctuating. There are a number of causes for the performance like entering the private players in insurance business and other corporations. However, LIC has made significant information in functioning related to annual premiums; Sum Assured and number of policies, it reach among customers. As the competition set tougher LIC will have to derive newer ways to retain its top position.

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